

Excess molar volumes and viscosities for binary mixtures of dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether and of dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether with 1-propanol and 2-propanol at 298.15 K

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Excess molar volumes (V_m^E) and viscosities (η) have been measured as a function of composition for binary liquid mixtures of dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether and of dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether with 1-propanol and 2-propanol at 298.15 K and atmospheric pressure. The V_m^E values for each of the mixture studied are negative over the whole composition range. The V_m^E results have been used to estimate the partial molar volumes of the components at infinite dilution. From the experimental data, the deviation in η from $\sum x_i \ln \eta_i$ have been calculated. The results are discussed as a basis to understand some of the molecular interactions present in the mixtures. The viscosity data have been correlated with the equations of McAllister, Heric, and Auslaender.

Mixtures containing oxygenated compounds, such as ethers (-O- group) and alkanols (-OH group), are of great importance from a practical point of view due to their increasingly use as additive to gasoline owing to their octane-enhancing and pollution reducing properties¹. Binary systems of alkoxypropanols and 1-alkanols might generate interesting properties due to their complexity, consequence of the self-association of the alkanols, specific interactions, hydrogen bond effects etc^{2,3}. A detailed understanding about the effect of the simultaneous presence of the ether and hydroxyl groups in the same molecule on the excess thermodynamic properties and the corresponding behavior of alkoxypropanols in mixtures with alkanols is thus an interesting topic for study.

In a previous paper⁴ we reported excess molar volumes (V_m^E) for the dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether + 1-propanol at 298.15 K. In the present paper we report V_m^E and viscosity (η) for mixtures of dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether (DPGMME), and dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether (DPGMBE) with 1-propanol or 2-propanol at 298.15 K and atmospheric pressure.

The results will of interest to ascertain whether the thermophysical properties of the dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether + 1-propanol or 2-propanol resemble those of dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether + 1-propanol or 2-propanol⁴. Comparison of the excess molar properties of dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether + 1-propanol or 2-propanol with those of propylene glycol monomethyl ether + 1-propanol or 2-propanol⁵ will enable us to comprehend

the effect of specific interactions on the excess properties, the dependence on the position of the OH group and the alkyl chain length in the alkanol, and the influence of the alkyl chain length as well as the polar head group of alkoxypropanols.

Results and discussion

Results of measurements of excess molar volumes of the different binary mixtures for a number of mole fractions at 298.15 K and at atmospheric pressure are given in Table 1. The plots of excess molar volume together with the smoothing curves against the mole fractions of the alkoxypropanol are given in Fig. 1.

Densities of liquid mixtures were calculated from the excess volume and composition according to the relation :

$$\rho = (x_1 M_1 + x_2 M_2) / (V_m^E + x_1 V_{m,1}^* + x_2 V_{m,2}^*) \quad (1)$$

where x_1 and x_2 are mole fractions, M_1 and M_2 are molar masses, and $V_{m,1}^*$ and $V_{m,2}^*$ are molar volumes of pure components 1 and 2, respectively.

The viscosities were fitted to a polynomial of type :

$$\eta = \sum A_i x_1^{i-1} \quad (2)$$

by the method of least-squares with equal weights assigned to each point. The values of coefficients A_i and standard deviation σ are listed in Table 2a.

The deviations of the viscosities were calculated from the relationship^{6,7} :

Table 1. Excess molar volumes and partial molar volumes for alkoxypropanol + alkanol systems at 298.15 K

x_1	$10^6 \times V_m^E$ $m^3 mol^{-1}$	$10^6 \times \bar{V}_{m,1}$ $m^3 mol^{-1}$	$10^6 \times \bar{V}_{m,2}$ $m^3 mol^{-1}$	x_1	$10^6 \times V_m^E$ $m^3 mol^{-1}$	$10^6 \times \bar{V}_{m,1}$ $m^3 mol^{-1}$	$10^6 \times \bar{V}_{m,2}$ $m^3 mol^{-1}$
Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether (1) + 2-propanol (2)							
0.0031	-0.003	154.469	76.909	0.3527	-0.213	155.203	76.892
0.0368	-0.032	154.574	77.001	0.3821	-0.220	155.231	76.849
0.0641	-0.062	154.649	77.052	0.3893	-0.221	155.238	76.839
0.0983	-0.091	154.740	77.088	0.4232	-0.228	155.265	76.789
0.1301	-0.120	154.819	77.101	0.4364	-0.230	155.275	76.770
0.1579	-0.134	154.884	77.098	0.4576	-0.235	155.289	76.739
0.1862	-0.154	154.945	77.085	0.4844	-0.236	155.305	76.701
0.2122	-0.171	154.997	77.066	0.5201	-0.234	155.324	76.649
0.2411	-0.184	155.049	77.037	0.5636	-0.233	155.344	76.584
0.2418	-0.184	155.050	77.036	0.6062	-0.231	155.363	76.519
0.2648	-0.196	155.088	77.010	0.6508	-0.226	155.384	76.445
0.2898	-0.199	155.125	76.979	0.7414	-0.207	155.431	76.266
0.2915	-0.201	155.128	76.977	0.7827	-0.196	155.456	76.166
0.3192	-0.206	155.164	76.939	0.8961	-0.122	155.526	75.797
0.3245	-0.209	155.170	76.932	0.9658	-0.047	155.556	75.486
Dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether (1) + 1-propanol (2)							
0.0177	-0.034	207.637	75.148	0.3003	-0.333	208.876	74.891
0.0340	-0.061	207.692	75.126	0.3251	-0.343	208.949	74.866
0.0472	-0.084	207.744	75.110	0.3476	-0.345	209.007	74.843
0.0639	-0.111	207.816	75.093	0.3602	-0.344	209.036	74.830
0.0881	-0.145	207.929	75.072	0.3838	-0.347	209.085	74.807
0.1001	-0.164	207.989	75.062	0.4162	-0.345	209.141	74.777
0.1130	-0.187	208.053	75.052	0.4517	-0.335	209.189	74.747
0.1349	-0.211	208.165	75.036	0.4963	-0.325	209.234	74.713
0.1599	-0.241	208.291	75.017	0.5453	-0.316	209.269	74.682
0.1788	-0.259	208.384	75.002	0.5953	-0.295	209.296	74.656
0.1855	-0.264	208.416	74.997	0.6420	-0.271	209.319	74.630
0.2028	-0.278	208.497	74.983	0.6718	-0.258	209.331	74.615
0.2192	-0.290	208.570	74.968	0.7831	-0.196	209.379	74.522
0.2369	-0.302	208.645	74.952	0.8711	-0.125	209.411	74.390
0.2488	-0.312	208.693	74.941	0.9026	-0.099	209.418	74.329
0.2580	-0.314	208.729	74.933	0.9584	-0.041	209.425	74.214
0.2889	-0.329	208.839	74.902				
Dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether (1) + 2-propanol (2)							
0.0198	-0.134	202.842	77.011	0.3696	-1.392	207.195	76.378
0.0567	-0.362	203.585	77.163	0.3871	-1.420	207.303	76.267
0.0897	-0.542	204.181	77.241	0.4283	-1.454	207.536	75.989
0.1165	-0.680	204.617	77.266	0.4639	-1.473	207.718	75.734
0.1447	-0.800	205.033	77.261	0.5003	-1.491	207.890	75.459
0.1763	-0.925	205.453	77.219	0.5619	-1.472	208.158	74.964
0.2007	-1.010	205.745	77.164	0.6315	-1.419	208.437	74.366
0.2140	-1.053	205.894	77.127	0.6839	-1.347	208.637	73.854
0.2389	-1.129	206.154	77.043	0.7368	-1.228	208.829	73.303
0.2543	-1.174	206.303	76.983	0.8165	-0.996	209.094	72.357
0.2799	-1.231	206.534	76.871	0.8739	-0.752	209.253	71.565
0.2926	-1.262	206.640	76.810	0.9044	-0.607	209.321	71.097
0.3131	-1.303	206.802	76.705	0.9334	-0.449	209.372	70.617
0.3372	-1.350	206.979	76.572	0.9659	-0.242	209.411	70.038
0.3659	-1.389	207.172	76.401				

$$\Delta \ln \eta = \ln \eta - (x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2) \quad (3)$$

where η is the dynamic viscosity of the mixtures and η_1 and η_2 are the viscosities of components 1 and 2, respectively.

Data on derived densities and viscosities at 298.15 K are given in Table 3. The mixing functions V_m^E and $\Delta \ln \eta$ were represented mathematically by the following type of

Fig. 1. Experimental excess molar volumes for dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether + 1-propanol, --- (ref. 3); + 2-propanol, ● and dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether + 1-propanol, Δ; + 2-propanol, ▲ at 298.15 K. Continuous curves were calculated from (3) for experimental data.

the Redlich-Kister equation⁸ for correlating the experimental data :

$$Y(x) = x_1 x_2 \sum_{i=1}^n A_i (x_1 - x_2)^{i-1} \quad (4)$$

where $Y(x)$ refers to $V_m^E \times 10^6 / \text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ or $\Delta \ln (\eta \times 10^3 / \text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1})$, x_1 and x_2 are the mole fraction of alkoxypropanol and alkanol, and A_i are the coefficients. The values of coefficients A_i were determined by a multiple regression analysis based on the least-squares method and are summarized along with the standard deviations between experimental and fitted values of the respective functions in Table 2b.

The standard deviation is defined by :

$$\sigma = \sum_{i=1}^m (Y(x)_{\text{exp}} - Y(x)_{\text{calc}})^2 / (m - n)^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

where m is the number of experimental point and n is the number of adjustable parameters. For all mixtures, $\sigma (V_m^E \times 10^6) \leq 0.003$, for the precision attainable with the dilatometer used. For the case of $\Delta \ln \eta$, the σ values lie between $0.006 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $0.004 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and the largest σ value correspond to dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether

Table 2.

(a) Coefficients A_i from (1) for viscosity $\eta \times 10^3 (\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1})$ and standard deviation σ

	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	A_5	σ
Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether (1) + 1-propanol (2)	1.9523	0.8922	1.2227	-0.6418		0.006
2-propanol (2)	2.0806	1.1526	-1.9550	4.3135	-2.0882	0.022
Dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether (1) + 1-propanol (2)	1.9524	3.4153	-0.8126	-0.0454		0.015
2-propanol (2)	2.0741	2.2919	1.4297	-1.3381		0.019

(b) Coefficients A_i from (3) and standard deviation η determined by the method of least squares

	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	A_5	σ
Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether (1) + 1-propanol (2)						
$\Delta \ln [\eta \times 10^3, \text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}]$	0.0540	0.0977	-0.0665	-0.0776		0.004
Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether (1) + 2-propanol (2)						
$V_m^E \times 10^6 (\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1})$	-0.9364	-0.0547	-0.4071	-0.1973		0.003
$\Delta \ln [\eta \times 10^3, \text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}]$	-0.1369	0.0256	-0.0744	0.0727	0.6407	0.006
Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether (1) + 1-propanol (2)						
$V_m^E \times 10^6 (\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1})$	-1.3081	0.5544	-0.4804	-0.1602	0.3464	0.002
$\Delta \ln [\eta \times 10^3, \text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}]$	0.6372	-0.1794	-0.1487	-0.0712	0.5116	0.004
Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether (1) + 2-propanol (2)						
$V_m^E \times 10^6 (\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1})$	-5.9458	-0.1999	-1.3847	-0.0516	0.0566	0.003
$\Delta \ln [\eta \times 10^3, \text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}]$	0.4239	0.0855	0.2405	-0.0989	-0.4696	0.004

+ 2-propanol at 298.15 K. There are no literature values of either V_m^E or η for these mixtures available for comparison.

The partial molar volumes $\bar{V}_{m,1}$ and $\bar{V}_{m,2}$ of the compo-

Table 3. Densities and viscosities for alkoxypropanol + alkanol systems at 298.15 K					
x_1	$10^{-6} \times \rho$ kg m ⁻³	$10^3 \times \eta$ kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	x_1	$10^{-6} \times \rho$ kg m ⁻³	$10^3 \times \eta$ kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether (1) + 1-propanol (2)					
0.0041	0.8007	1.956	0.5470	0.9104	2.705
0.0244	0.8070	1.982	0.5820	0.9147	2.759
0.0588	0.8172	2.009	0.6212	0.9192	2.824
0.0904	0.8259	2.035	0.6597	0.9235	2.878
0.1407	0.8388	2.097	0.7459	0.9322	3.029
0.1832	0.8488	2.149	0.8219	0.9391	3.159
0.2635	0.8658	2.262	0.8662	0.9428	3.230
0.2900	0.8708	2.302	0.9199	0.9470	3.315
0.3284	0.8789	2.654	0.9454	0.9489	3.335
0.3894	0.8881	2.448	0.9798	0.9513	3.399
0.4745	0.9008	2.587			
Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether (1) + 2-propanol (2)					
0.0039	0.7829	2.082	0.5128	0.8998	2.604
0.0124	0.7859	2.094	0.5815	0.9095	2.709
0.0272	0.7911	2.112	0.6549	0.9189	2.833
0.0739	0.8062	2.159	0.7462	0.9293	2.987
0.1208	0.8200	2.202	0.7906	0.9340	3.072
0.1912	0.8385	2.258	0.8372	0.9386	3.146
0.2462	0.8514	2.302	0.8711	0.9418	3.222
0.2937	0.8616	2.339	0.8936	0.9438	3.331
0.3036	0.8636	2.348	0.9153	0.9457	3.399
0.3578	0.8741	2.402	0.9709	0.9504	3.444
0.4068	0.8829	2.459	0.9836	0.9514	3.449
0.4580	0.8914	2.522			
Dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether (1) + 1-propanol (2)					
0.0030	0.8003	1.949	0.3928	0.8716	3.167
0.0078	0.8018	1.975	0.4307	0.8755	3.279
0.0269	0.8075	2.048	0.4789	0.8799	3.422
0.0526	0.8146	2.133	0.5345	0.8846	3.524
0.0797	0.8214	2.246	0.6009	0.8896	3.694
0.1443	0.8355	2.436	0.6750	0.8943	3.872
0.1954	0.8449	2.571	0.7735	0.8997	4.094
0.2129	0.8479	2.625	0.8290	0.9023	4.187
0.2629	0.8556	2.780	0.8853	0.9046	4.305
0.3036	0.8611	2.922	0.9251	0.9061	4.397
0.3488	0.8667	3.040	0.9793	0.9079	4.469
Dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether (1) + 2-propanol (2)					
0.0031	0.7828	2.082	0.4984	0.8835	3.389
0.0145	0.7875	2.103	0.5731	0.8898	3.599
0.0350	0.7953	2.153	0.6346	0.8941	3.760
0.0595	0.8040	2.215	0.6784	0.8969	3.876
0.0859	0.8125	2.279	0.7780	0.9019	4.150
0.1240	0.8235	2.380	0.8305	0.9041	4.174
0.1869	0.8387	2.549	0.8767	0.9057	4.263
0.2417	0.8497	2.705	0.9155	0.9068	4.333
0.2676	0.8543	2.774	0.9416	0.9075	4.382
0.3393	0.8654	2.963	0.9750	0.9082	4.437
0.4325	0.8769	3.206			

nents, listed in Table 1, were evaluated^{9,10} over the whole composition range by way of eqs. (6) and (7) :

$$\bar{V}_{m,1} = V_m^E + V_{m,1}^* + (1 - x_1) (\partial V_m^E / \partial x_1)_{P,T} \quad (6)$$

and

$$\bar{V}_{m,2} = V_m^E + V_{m,2}^* + (1 - x_2) (\partial V_m^E / \partial x_2)_{P,T} \quad (7)$$

The derivative of eqs. (6) and (7) were obtained by differentiation of V_m^E from eq. (4). It leads to eqs. (8) and (9) for the partial molar volumes of the solute alkoxypropanol (1) ($\bar{V}_{m,1}$) and the co-solvent alkanol (2) ($\bar{V}_{m,2}$).

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{V}_{m,1} = & V_{m,1}^* + (1 - x_1)^2 \sum_{i=1}^n A_i (2x_1 - 1)^{i-1} \\ & + (1 - x_1)^2 x_1 \sum_{i=1}^n 2(i-1) A_i (2x_1 - 1)^{(i-2)} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{V}_{m,2} = & V_{m,2}^* + (1 - x_2)^2 \sum_{i=1}^n A_i (1 - 2x_2)^{i-1} \\ & + x_2(1 - x_2)^2 x_1 \sum_{i=1}^n (-2)(i-1) A_i (1 - 2x_2)^{(i-2)} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The partial molar volumes of alkoxypropanol at infinite dilution ($x_1 = 0$) in alkanol and the partial molar volume of alkanol at infinite dilution ($x_2 = 0$) in alkoxypropanol were obtained from eq. (8) by assuming $x_2 = 1$ (corresponding to $x_1 = 0$). Eq. (8) leads to :

$$\bar{V}_{m,1}^0 = V_{m,1}^* + \sum_{i=1}^n A_i (-1)^{i-1} \quad (10)$$

Similarly, assuming $x_2 = 0$ in equation (9) leads to :

$$\bar{V}_{m,2}^0 = V_{m,2}^* + \sum_{i=1}^n A_i \quad (11)$$

In eqs. (10) and (11), $\bar{V}_{m,1}^0$ and $\bar{V}_{m,2}^0$ represent the partial molar volume of alkoxypropanol at infinite dilution in alkanol and the partial molar volume of alkanol at infinite dilution in alkoxypropanol, respectively. Partial molar volumes at infinite dilution were evaluated by using the Redlich-Kister coefficients (Table 2b).

The observed excess molar volumes are negative over the whole range of composition for all the systems. Fig. 1

also shows that the excess molar volumes of dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether + 1-propanol⁴ mixtures. There are striking differences between the curves of the excess molar volumes of dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether + 1-propanol or 2-propanol and dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether + 1-propanol or 2-propanol mixtures, as is evident in Fig. 1. The excess molar volumes of the former system are less negative than those of the latter ones, on increasing of the alkyl chain in dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether results in a decrease in V_m^E with 1-propanol and 2-propanol. Remarkably, V_m^E is negative for the mixtures with 2-propanol as compared to 1-propanol. But in the case of dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether, V_m^E is more negative with 2-propanol. The large negative values indicates a reasonably strong association between the dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether and 2-propanol. Similar to those observed for mixtures of propan-1,2-diol with 1-propanol or 2-propanol⁵: V_m^E value is more negative with 2-propanol. This behavior may be compared with the V_m^E results for the mixtures alkoxypropanols with ethanol¹¹: V_m^E increases with the increasing the chain length of the *n*-alkanol. Again, one can generate a comparison of propylene glycol monomethyl ether⁵ and dipropylene glycol mono-methyl ether either with 1-propanol or 2-propanol systems. These results show that V_m^E values decreases as the number of OC_3H_6 group in the alkoxypropanol molecules increases but with less significant change. The similar behavior can also seen in the work of Cobos *et al.*² for mixtures of alkoxyethanols with 1-butanol and Pal and Sharma¹² for mixtures of alkoxyethanols with 1-propanol.

The magnitude of the excess molar volume decreases with the size and shape of the ether in mixtures containing 1-propanol or 2-propanol. The experimental results suggest that the volume behaviors of these mixtures are the result of several physical and chemical effects^{13,14}: disruption of liquid order on mixing and unfavorable interactions between unlike molecules producing a positive contribution to V_m^E , differences in molecular volumes and free volumes¹³ between liquid components, and possible association by hydrogen bonds producing a negative contribution to V_m^E .

We have determined the viscosities (η) and calculated the deviation in viscosity ($\Delta \ln \eta$) for the different binary mixtures over the whole mole fraction range. Fig. 2 shows that the viscosity deviations are positive for dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether + 1-propanol or 2-propanol systems and change sign for dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether + 1-propanol or 2-propanol systems. These results and those from Tu *et al.*¹¹, show that, the magnitude of the positive deviation increases as the alkyl chain length or viscosity of

Fig. 2. Experimental viscosity deviations for dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether + 1-propanol, o; + 2-propanol, ● and dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether + 1-propanol, Δ; + 2-propanol, ▲ at 298.15 K. Continuous curves were calculated from (3) for experimental data.

the *n*-alkanol increased. There is a very obvious increase in the magnitude of the $\Delta \ln \eta$ with the alkyl chain end length¹¹ or the number of $-\text{OC}_3\text{H}_6-$ group increase in the alkoxypropanol molecules. The similar behavior can also be seen for the mixtures of alkoxypropanols with 1-propanol¹². The positive $\Delta \ln \eta$ suggests the specific interactions present in the mixtures¹⁶. The strong positive deviations in the viscosity for dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether + 1-propanol or 2-propanol would imply that (i) the mixture is more viscous than the corresponding ideal mixture and (ii) the specific interactions results in a negative V_m^E , shown in Fig. 1.

Partial molar volumes of ether at infinite dilution $\bar{V}_{m,1}^0$ alkanols are listed in Table 4. All of these $\bar{V}_{m,1}^0$ values for ether in various cosolvents are smaller than the corresponding $V_{m,1}^*$ values of pure ether. This observation is consistent with the idea that the molar volume of ether (dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether or dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether) is the result of the actual molecular volume plus the empty volume that arises from the inter- and intramolecular self-association of pure ether molecule.

We also note that all the $\bar{V}_{m,2}^0$ values for various cosolvents in ethers listed in Table 4 are smaller than the corresponding $V_{m,2}^*$ values of the cosolvent. One can say that cosolvent molecules partially fitting into open or empty spaces in structured liquid ether result in negative excess volume. This is very important in the dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether + 2-propanol mixture.

We also observe that the partial molar volume of ether in alkanol decrease in the sequence 1-propanol to 2-propanol. The difference between $\bar{V}_{m,1}^0$ and $V_{m,1}^*$ values for dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether or dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether in various cosolvents (Table 4) decreases from 1-propanol to 2-propanol. This observation and also the negative V_m^E values of these systems lead us to suggest that the interaction between unlike molecules is more important than the structure breaking effect between like molecules. These interactions are relative strong between dipropylene glycol

glycol monomethyl ether, $V_{m,1}^E$ results in more smoother curves, indicating less self-association. This reflects the breaking of the self-associated ether and alkanol molecules at lower and higher x_1 and the formation of hydrogen bonds between unlike molecules. This is very important in the dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether + 2-propanol mixture.

McAllister's multibody interaction model¹⁷ is widely used for correlating the kinematic viscosity of liquid mixtures with the mole fraction. The four-body model is defined as :

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \nu = & x_1^4 \ln \nu_1 + 4 x_1^3 x_2 \ln Z_{1112} + 6 x_1^2 x_2^2 \ln Z_{1122} \\ & + 4 x_1 x_2^3 \ln Z_{2221} + x_2^4 \ln \nu_2 - \ln [x_1 + x_2 (M_2/M_1)] \\ & + 4 x_1^3 x_2 \ln [(3 + M_2/M_1)/4] + 6 x_1^2 x_2^2 \ln \\ & [(1 + M_2/M_1)/2] + 4 x_1 x_2^3 \ln [(1 + 3M_2/M_1)/4] \\ & + x_2^4 \ln (M_2/M_1) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where Z_{1112} , Z_{1122} , and Z_{2221} are interaction parameters.

Heric⁷ suggested relation (13) for correlating the kinematic viscosity of the binary liquid mixtures :

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \nu = & x_1 \ln \nu_1 + x_2 \ln \nu_2 + x_1 \ln M_1 + x_2 \ln M_2 \\ & - \ln (x_1 M_1 + x_2 M_2) + x_1 x_2 [A + B (x_1 - x_2) \\ & + C (x_1 - x_2)^2] \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where A , B , and C are adjustable parameters.

Auslaender¹⁸ developed expression (14) for the kinematic viscosity of binary mixtures :

$$x_1(x_1 + B_{12}x_2)(\nu - \nu_1) + A_{21}x_2(B_{21}x_2 + x_2)(\nu - \nu_2) = 0 \quad (14)$$

where B_{12} , A_{21} , and B_{21} are the parameters containing 12 interactions. The parameters of the viscosity equations calculated with the help of least-squares procedure and the percentage standard deviations σ (%) between the experimental and calculated values are given in Table 5. It is observed that McAllister's four-body interaction model correlates both the mixtures viscosity and the mixture den-

Table 4. Partial molar volume of alkoxypropanol (1) or alkanol (2) at infinite dilution in alkanol (2) or alkoxypropanol (1) at 298. 15 K

System	$10^6 \times V_{m,1}^*$ $\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	$10^6 \times \bar{V}_{m,1}^0$ $\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	$10^6 \times V_{m,2}^*$ $\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	$10^6 \times \bar{V}_{m,2}^0$ $\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$
Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether (1) +				
1-propanol (2)	155.56	154.54 ^a	75.18	74.7 ^a
2-propanol (2)	155.56	154.47	76.89	75.30
Dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether (1) +				
1-propanol (2)	209.43	207.59	75.18	74.13
2-propanol (2)	209.43	202.40	76.89	69.37

^aRef. 4.

monomethyl ether or dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether and 2-propanol, as suggested from V_m^E data.

Analysis of the excess partial molar volume curves, $V_{m,1}^E$ (ether) and $V_{m,2}^E$ (alkanol) calculated from eq. (4) suggested that the difference between $V_{m,1}^E$ and $V_{m,2}^E$ is the changes in curvature found for $V_{m,1}^E$ of dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether indicating the stronger self-association. For dipropylene

Table 5. Values of the parameters and percentage standard deviation for alkoxypropanol + alkanol systems represented by eqns. (12–14)

Eq. (12)				Eq. (13)				Eq. (14)			
Z_{1112}	Z_{1122}	Z_{2221}	$\sigma\%$	A	B	C	$\sigma\%$	B_{12}	B_{21}	A_{21}	$\sigma\%$
Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether (1) + 1-propanol (2)											
0.90	1.47	1.11	0.10	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.31	0.09	0.21	0.19	0.62
Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether (1) + 2-propanol (2)											
0.95	1.63	1.23	0.40	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.62	0.18	0.22	0.88	0.73
Dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether (1) + 1-propanol (2)											
1.28	1.96	1.51	0.25	0.06	0.12	0.26	2.49	0.26	0.08	0.19	2.15
Dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether (1) + 2-propanol (2)											
1.26	2.02	1.34	0.33	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.56	0.22	0.17	0.25	1.27

sity to a significantly high degree of accuracy than both Heric and Auslaender equations as evidenced by small percentage standard deviations.

Table 6. Densities and viscosities of pure components at 298.15 K

Substance	$10^{-3} \times \rho$ (kg m ⁻³)		$10^{-3} \times \eta$ (kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	
	Exp.	Lit.	Exp.	Lit.
Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether	0.9527	0.9510 ^a	3.455	3.691 ^a
Dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether	0.9086	0.9089 ^a	4.489	4.503 ^a
1-Propanol	0.7994	0.7995 ^b 0.79960 ^c	1.942	1.941 ^b 1.943 ^c 1.944 ^d
2-Propanol	0.7815	0.78126 ^c 0.7813 ^e 0.7812 ^f	2.075	2.0436 ^c 2.049 ^e 2.052 ^g

^aRef. 11, ^bRef. 20, ^cRef. 21, ^dRef. 22, ^eRef. 23, ^fRef. 24, ^gRef. 25.

Experimental

Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether (Merck, Schuchardt, GC > 95%) and 1-propanol (SRL, Mumbai, minimum assay 99.5%) were the same as used earlier⁴. Dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether (Aldrich, 99%) was used as such. 2-Propanol (S.D.Fine, A.R. 99.5%) was purified¹⁹. All samples were stored and protected from atmospheric moisture and CO₂. Before measurements, the samples were partially degassed under vacuum and dried over 0.4 nm molecular sieves to reduce water content. The densities and viscosities of these liquids were measured and compared at 298.15 ± 0.01 K and atmospheric pressure with their literature values^{11,20–25} (Table 6). The densities were measured with a bicapillary pycnometer that gave an estimated accuracy of 5 parts in 10⁵. The pycnometer was calibrated at 298.15 ± 0.01 K with triple-distilled water.

Excess molar volumes (reproducible to ±0.003 × 10⁻⁶ m³ mol⁻¹) were measured directly with a continuous dilution dilatometer²⁶. Details of its calibration, experimental set-up, and operational procedures have been described earlier^{27,28}.

The kinematic viscosities (ν) of pure liquids and liquid mixtures were measured at 298.15 K and at atmospheric pressure using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscosimeter²⁹. The details of the apparatus and procedure have been given earlier^{30,31}.

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